

solverCan: A Mathematical Function Solver from Dataset Using Forward Differences, Derivative Ratio Analysis, and Iterative Residual Correction

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March 2026

Abstract

This paper presents **solverCan**, a Python library that identifies mathematical functions from raw numerical data without requiring prior knowledge of the function type. The library employs a combination of forward difference analysis with Coefficient of Variation (CV) detection, Gaussian elimination for polynomial coefficient extraction, derivative ratio analysis for exponential function identification, and iterative residual correction for complex functions. Unlike machine learning approaches, solverCan produces explicit, human-readable equations and operates effectively with as few as 7–10 data points. The library automatically selects the best-fitting method among polynomial, exponential, iterative, and piecewise approaches, achieving less than 0.01% deviation for polynomial and exponential data, and less than 5% for trigonometric and irrational functions. The library is publicly available via PyPI (`pip install solverCan`).

Keywords: numerical analysis, function approximation, forward differences, derivative ratios, polynomial fitting, exponential detection, piecewise approximation, Python library

1 Introduction

Determining the underlying mathematical function from a set of observed data points is a fundamental problem in numerical analysis, engineering, and data science. Traditional approaches include least-squares regression (which requires specifying the function form a priori), machine learning models (which require large datasets and produce black-box predictions), and curve fitting libraries such as `scipy.optimize.curve_fit` (which require initial parameter guesses and function form specification).

This paper presents a method that addresses these limitations by providing an automated pipeline that:

- Detects the function type (polynomial, exponential, trigonometric, irrational) automatically
- Requires only 7–10 data points
- Produces explicit, human-readable equations
- Uses no external numerical libraries (pure Python implementation)
- Combines multiple classical methods with novel iterative correction

The method starts from Newton's forward difference formula with unit step size ($h = 1$). Given discrete data points $f(1), f(2), \dots, f(n)$, the forward difference approximates the derivative:

$$\Delta f(x) = f(x+1) - f(x) \quad (1)$$

By applying successive forward differences, polynomial functions reach a constant value after n steps (where n is the degree). This constant is then integrated back n times to recover the original equation. For non-polynomial functions, derivative ratio analysis and iterative correction extend the approach.

2 Methodology

2.1 Forward Difference Analysis and Degree Detection

For a polynomial of degree n , the n -th forward difference yields a constant. To detect when this constant is reached, we compute the Coefficient of Variation (CV) at each difference level:

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where μ is the mean of absolute values and σ is the standard deviation of absolute values at each forward difference level. When $CV < 2\%$, the polynomial degree is identified.

Table 1: CV thresholds for degree detection

CV Range	Interpretation	Action
$CV < 0.01\%$	Values are constant	Polynomial degree found
$CV < 2\%$	Values are very close	Degree detected (threshold)
$CV > 50\%$	Values differ significantly	Continue to next difference

2.2 Gaussian Elimination for Coefficient Extraction

Once the degree n is determined, an $(n+1) \times (n+1)$ linear system is constructed using the first $n+1$ data points. For data points (x_i, y_i) and polynomial $f(x) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + \dots + a_nx^n$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_1 & x_1^2 & \cdots & x_1^n \\ 1 & x_2 & x_2^2 & \cdots & x_2^n \\ \vdots & & & & \vdots \\ 1 & x_{n+1} & x_{n+1}^2 & \cdots & x_{n+1}^n \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ \vdots \\ a_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ \vdots \\ y_{n+1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

This system is solved via Gaussian elimination with partial pivoting.

2.3 Derivative Ratio Analysis for Exponential Detection

For exponential functions $f(x) = A \cdot e^{ax} + c$, the ratio of consecutive forward difference values is constant:

$$\frac{\Delta f(x+1)}{\Delta f(x)} = e^a = \text{constant} \quad (4)$$

If the CV of these ratios falls below 0.1%, an exponential structure is confirmed. The exponential parameter is extracted via:

$$a = \ln(\text{ratio}) \tag{5}$$

The amplitude A and offset c are determined by back-integration and initial value matching. For the salt tank problem presented in Section 3.3, this method correctly identifies $a = -3/50 = -0.06$ from a constant ratio of 0.94176.

2.4 Iterative Residual Correction

For functions that are not purely polynomial or exponential, `solverCan` employs an iterative correction method:

1. Find polynomial approximation $f_1(x)$ from data
2. Compute residual: $r(x) = \text{original} - f_1(x)$
3. Find polynomial approximation $f_2(x)$ from residual
4. Sum: $f_{\text{total}}(x) = f_1(x) + f_2(x)$
5. Repeat until residual converges to zero

This approach is analogous to a Taylor-like expansion and effectively captures complex function behavior through successive polynomial corrections. The number of iterations can be controlled via the `max_iter` parameter.

2.5 Piecewise Polynomial Approximation

For functions with varying behavior across the domain (e.g., trigonometric functions), `solverCan` splits the data at deviation breakpoints:

1. Fit polynomial to first N training points
2. Test forward: check deviation at each subsequent point
3. When deviation exceeds threshold (default: 5%), split
4. Start new segment from the split point

$$5. \text{ Result: piecewise function } f(x) = \begin{cases} f_1(x) & x \in [a, b] \\ f_2(x) & x \in [b, c] \\ \vdots & \end{cases}$$

2.6 Automatic Method Selection

The `auto()` function tries all available methods (polynomial, exponential, iterative, piecewise), evaluates each on the training data using maximum deviation as the score, and returns the result with the lowest deviation.

Table 2: Forward differences for polynomial example

x	$f(x)$	$\Delta^1 f$	$\Delta^2 f$
1	14	-1	2
2	13	1	2
3	14	3	2
4	17	5	2
5	22	7	2
6	29	9	2
7	38	11	2
8	49	13	
9	62	15	
10	77		

3 Worked Examples

3.1 Example 1: Polynomial Detection

Given the dataset $y = \{14, 13, 14, 17, 22, 29, 38, 49, 62, 77\}$ for $x = 1, 2, \dots, 10$:

The second forward difference is constant ($\Delta^2 f = 2$), confirming degree 2. After Gaussian elimination:

$$f(x) = x^2 - 4x + 17 \tag{6}$$

All 10 data points match with 0.0000% deviation.

3.2 Example 2: Trigonometric Function with Iterative Correction

For the function $d(a) = (10 + 10 \cos a)(10 + 10 \sin a)$ evaluated at angles 1–9 degrees, the method applies forward differences to find a first approximation:

$$f(x) = -\frac{13x^3}{30000} - 0.0074x^2 + 3.495233x + 196.5126 \tag{7}$$

Computing the residual between original data and $f(x)$ and applying the method again yields a correction:

$$f_{\text{correction}}(x) = 0.01115x - \frac{157x^2}{20000} + 3.4841 \tag{8}$$

The total function $f_{\text{total}}(x) = f(x) + f_{\text{correction}}(x)$ achieves 98–100% similarity for the first 45 degrees.

3.3 Example 3: Exponential Function — Salt Tank Problem

A 50-liter tank initially containing pure water receives salt solution (2 g/L) at 3 L/s. The differential equation solution gives $f(t) = 100 - 100e^{-3t/50}$.

Given only the data points, the derivative ratio analysis finds a constant ratio of 0.94176 at the first derivative level:

$$e^a = 0.94176 \implies a = \ln(0.94176) = -0.06 = -\frac{3}{50} \tag{9}$$

After iterative correction, the method converges to the exact solution:

$$f_{\text{total5}}(t) = 100.0001 - 100 \cdot e^{-3t/50} \tag{10}$$

Table 3: Convergence of iterative correction for exponential function

Iteration	Equation	Constant
f_{new}	$21.52 - (50/3)e^{-3t/50}$	21.52
f_{total}	$37.22 - (100/3)e^{-3t/50}$	37.22
$f_{\text{total}2}$	$52.91 - 50e^{-3t/50}$	52.91
$f_{\text{total}3}$	$68.61 - (200/3)e^{-3t/50}$	68.61
$f_{\text{total}4}$	$84.30 - (250/3)e^{-3t/50}$	84.30
$f_{\text{total}5}$	$100.00 - 100e^{-3t/50}$	100.00

4 Library Results

The methods were implemented in the solverCan Python library. Table 4 summarizes the automated test results.

Table 4: solverCan auto-detection results (10 data points)

Function Type	Example	Method Selected	Max Dev.
Polynomial	$x^2 - 4x + 17$	Polynomial (deg 2)	0.00%
Exponential	$100 - 100e^{-0.06x}$	Derivative Ratios	0.003%
Exponential	$50000 \cdot e^{0.03x}$	Derivative Ratios	0.006%
Trigonometric	$(10 + 10 \cos)(10 + 10 \sin)$	Piecewise (2 pcs)	2.11%
Irrational	$x^2 + 24 - \sqrt{x}$	Polynomial (deg 2)	1.57%
Mixed	$24x^3 + \sin(x)$	Iterative (2 iter)	0.0002%

4.1 Population Growth Prediction

For $P(t) = 50,000 \cdot e^{0.03t}$ with 10 data points, solverCan correctly identified the growth rate ($a = 0.02999$ vs actual 0.03) with prediction accuracy of 2.97% at $t = 20$ (10 years beyond training data).

5 API Reference

The library provides the following methods:

Table 5: solverCan API

Method	Description	Best For
<code>solverCan.plynm(y)</code>	Polynomial	Polynomial data
<code>solverCan.expo(y)</code>	Exponential	Growth/decay
<code>solverCan.trig(y)</code>	Piecewise	Oscillating data
<code>solverCan.trigOneEq(y)</code>	Single equation	Training range
<code>solverCan.irrational(y)</code>	Piecewise	\sqrt{x} , ln data
<code>solverCan.auto(y)</code>	Auto-select	Unknown data
<code>solverCan.table(y, fn)</code>	Comparison table	Verification
<code>solverCan.compare_graph(y, fn)</code>	Chart (PNG)	Visualization

All methods return a dictionary containing `equation` (string), `compute` (callable function), and `method` (string). The `compute` function can be called with any x value to predict $f(x)$.

6 Limitations and Future Work

- **Logistic functions:** S-curve functions $P(t) = K/(1 + be^{-ct})$ are not yet supported as a dedicated method.
- **Noisy data:** The library assumes clean data. A genetic algorithm (GA) based noise reduction approach is under development, where GA shifts data points within tolerance to find the simplest underlying equation.
- **Extrapolation:** Polynomial approximations diverge for predictions far outside the training range. Exponential methods are more robust for extrapolation.
- **Multi-variable:** Currently limited to single-variable functions $f(x)$.

Future versions may include: logistic function detection, GA-based noise-tolerant fitting, Fourier-based trigonometric detection, and multi-variable support.

7 Conclusion

solverCan demonstrates that classical numerical methods — forward differences, Gaussian elimination, and derivative ratio analysis — when combined with automated detection heuristics and iterative residual correction, can effectively reverse-engineer mathematical functions from small datasets (7–10 points). The approach is fully transparent, producing human-readable equations rather than black-box predictions. The library achieves exact results for polynomial data, sub-0.01% deviation for exponential data, and below 5% for trigonometric and irrational functions.

Availability

The library is open source under MIT License and available at:

- PyPI: <https://pypi.org/project/solverCan/>
- Installation: `pip install solverCan`

References

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